

Montecarlo simulations and Sankey Diagrams: Swenson process of sugarcane raw wax production.

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Appendix C - Montecarlo simulations (MCS) for Brazil-Bahia and Cuba, Heptane and Toluene.

(C)

(D)

Figure C1. MCS for IPCC 2021 - GWP 100 impact category, (A) - Brazil-Bahia, Heptane; (B) - Cuba, Heptane (C) - Brazil-Bahia, Toluene;; (D) – Cuba, Toluene.

Appendix D - Sankey Diagrams of Swenson process of sugarcane raw wax production, to Brazil and Cuba, Heptane and Toluene.

(A)

(B)

(C)

(D)

Figure D1. Sankey diagrams of GWP 100 impact resulting from Swenson process of sugarcane raw wax production, (A) - Brazil-Bahia, Heptane; (B) – Cuba, Heptane; (C) - Brazil-Bahia, Toluene; (D) - Cuba, Toluene.